

A Synchronized Approach to Outlier Detection with Application to Econometrics Data in Nigeria Economy

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Abstract

Outliers could be additive, innovative or mixed, depending on whether it affects a single observation; where it serves as an unusual innovation in the generating process affecting all later observations or when only one characteristic of the series is changed by the innovation. (Hawkins (1980), Denby & Martin (1979) and Draper & Smith (1984)). Modification of Outliers generally improves the forecasting performance of a time series model because it is believed that outliers occur at places where the process generating the series has temporarily broken down which call for the modification of the outliers to compensate for the forecast calculations. Forty-one years data set was collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria; including records on the Gross Domestic Product at current price, Real Estate, Information and Communication, Servicing, Mining and Quarrying and Agriculture sector of the economy..The time series data is subjected to stationarity test and thereafter we determined the level at which the data set is useful for analysis. High σ^2 estimate and a high AIC coefficient adopted as an accuracy measurement indicate an improvement after adjusting for outliers in the model for the prediction of GDP in Nigeria.

Key Words: Gross Domestic Product, Outlier, Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average, Time Series Analysis, Econometric Indicator, Unit Root-test

1. Introduction

Anomalies have recently been increasingly studied in the statistical time series literature, and this interest is also growing in econometrics. Generally, outliers in a time series are informally defined as unexpected or surprising values occurring relative to the rest of the series. Potentially valuable information for public and private policy making often occurs in the form of time series. Most time series data are observational in nature. In addition to possible gross errors, time series data are often affected by a number of uncontrolled or unexpected measures; for example, the implementation of a new regulation, important changes in political or economic policy, or the occurrence of a disaster. Treating an observation as an outlier has been, and continues to be, a major problem in statistical inference. There is no generally accepted definition of abnormality. Hawkins (1980) proposed the following intuitive definition: "An outlier is an observation that is

so different from other observations as to raise suspicion that it was produced by a different mechanism." Therefore, conflicting observations and different structural changes often appear in time series data. Although the standard time series model is designed to understand the homogeneous memory pattern of a time series, the presence of outliers depending on their nature, can have a moderate or significant effect on the effectiveness of the standard time series analysis methodology, detection, evaluation and predictive modelling. Wang & Mao (2018) Therefore, there is a clear need for available methods to detect or adjust them. Outliers are detected in most irregular series using a threshold that is a multiple of the mean square of the corresponding interval in the series. However, the commonly used default selection accounts for a large proportion of the outliers, perhaps 10% of the observations, and it seems unlikely that the generation process is often interrupted. Tsay (1986)

The study of outliers is not a new phenomenon. It actually has a long history, dating back to the earliest statistical analysis. Neighbouring methods developed hand in hand with other statistical methods. Unfortunately, this expansion of singular methods has not been as rapid and widespread in time series analysis. One of the reasons for this is probably that the methods of time series deviations were first explicitly investigated. Since then, however, the number of articles on this topic has steadily increased (Rousseeuw and Bossche 2018). Deviations and structural changes are often encountered when analyzing time series data. The presence of these extraordinary events can easily mislead the standard time series analysis procedure and lead to erroneous conclusions. However, the effect of these events is often overlooked due to the lack of simple but useful methods to deal with the dynamic behaviour of these events in the underlying sequence. Therefore, the primary objective of this paper is to review unified methods for detecting and handling outliers and structural changes in one-dimensional time series. The deviations in question are additive deviation (AO) and innovation deviation. Allowed structural changes are level change (LS) and variance change (VC). Level change is further classified as permanent level change (LC) and transient level change (TC) (Rousseeuw et al. 2019). Hillmer, Bell, and Tiao (1983) (henceforth HBT, hereafter "current bias") used a more rigorous approach to handling biases in model-based seasonal smoothing. They showed how model residual errors can be used with a certain threshold to detect different types of outliers. It is important to develop techniques that can be applied to a financial situation to detect anomalies in historical and real-time data. The purpose of this study is to bring recently developed methods for dealing with three common time series deviations into a financial context using an autoregressive integrated moving average model. Recently, despite many studies investigating the effect of outliers on model building, studies emphasizing the detection of both local and global outliers in a dataset have been found to be superseded when they lead to interpretation, prediction, or prediction of values. . Therefore, it is clearer to study the effect of anomalies in the econometric data of Nigerian financial records.

Specifically, this study examines the impact of anomalies arising from the Nigerian microeconomic system on time-dependent data. Empirically, this study covers the period from

1981 to 2020. To examine the Nigerian experience in an economic context, the study looked at two distinct periods or eras. The archival data for this study covers the period 1981 to 2020 and was obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin 2022. The study period spans 41 years, much longer than the usual 10 years. -15 years. to study time series. The choice of 2020 as the centre or focus of this research is due to the fact that the era of covid-19 has returned to the country, which has affected the economy of the largest countries in the world.

2. Methods and Materials

Auto Regressive Moving Average

The ARMA model, or Autoregressive Moving Average model, is used to describe weakly stationary stochastic time series with two polynomials. The first of these polynomials is for autoregression, the second for moving average (Chen and Liu, (1993)). Autoregressive moving average (ARMA) is the basic model for stationary time series analysis. Firstly, stationarity must be formally defined through the behaviour of the autocorrelation function (ACF) through global decay. Several simple cases of the ARMA model are then presented and analyzed, and the partial autocorrelation function (PACF) is also defined, before introducing the general model. The construction and estimation of an ARMA model can then be developed and is done through a series of examples that aim to show some of the subtleties in choosing an appropriate model to explain the evolution of the observed time series (Johansen and Nielsen, 2016). Often this model is called an ARMA(p,q) model; where:

- p is the order of the autoregressive polynomial,
- q is the order of the moving average polynomial.

The equation is given by:

$$X_t = c + \varepsilon_t + \sum_{i=1}^p \varphi_i X_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \theta_i \varepsilon_{t-i}.$$

Where:

- φ = the autoregressive model's parameters,
- θ = the moving average model's parameters.
- c = a constant,
- ε = error terms (white noise).

As we noted, dependence is very common in time series observations. To model this time series dependence, we start with univariate ARMA models. To motivate the model, we can basically proceed from two lines of thought. First, the set x_t can be modelled such that the level of its current observations depends on the level of its lagged observations (Li et al. 2015). For example, if we observe a high realization of GDP in this quarter, we assume that GDP will be good in the following quarters as well. This way of thinking can be represented by an AR model. AR(1) (first order autoregressive) can be written as:

$$x_t = \phi x_{t-1} + \xi_t$$

We introduced the ARMA model that may be written as:

$$\varphi(B)Z_t = c + \theta(B)a_t$$

The above equation model can be directly extended to include divergence messages to induce stationarity and seasonal expressions (such as multiplicative AR or MA operators). West (1986) We focus our discussion on non-seasonal patterns to facilitate our understanding of anomalies. We also assume that $C=0$ so that we can rewrite in the form:

$$Z_t = \frac{\phi(B)}{1-\phi(B)} a_t$$

In the above model, z_t represents the series uncontaminated by outliers. We use $Y_t z_t$ to represent the observed values in the presence of an outlier. As we can see, our deviation representation is in the form of an intervention model. The AR operator (and the difference operator, if present) is placed in the denominator of the ARIMA model. Therefore, the effect of bias is relative to Y_t rather than AR-filtered Y_t (Reiche et al. 2015). We now define and illustrate the types of deviations. These include additive deviation (AO), innovative deviation (IO), level shift (LS), and temporary (or temporary) change (TC), and to illustrate the effect of each type of deviation and its effect on the time series, suppose we have AR (1), then the following simple AR process is used:

$$Z_t = \frac{1}{1-\phi B} a_t$$

3. Analysis

Table 1.1: Unit-Root Test Analysis with Outlier

Variable		at level	at first difference	at second difference	at third difference	Equation Specification	Order of integration
AGR	ADF	1.042857 (0.9953)	- 4.131966 (0.0053)	-4.131966 (0.0053)	--	Trend and intercept	I(1)
	PP	1.042857 (0.9953)	- 4.131966 (0.0053)	-4.131966 (0.0053)	--	Trend and intercept	I(1)
M&QURR	ADF	- 0.201952 (0.9235)	- 4.411159 (0.0030)	-4.411159 (0.0030)	--	Trend and intercept	I(1)
	PP	0.206442 (0.9656)	- 4.628597 (0.0019)	-4.628597 (0.0019)	--	Trend and intercept	I(1)
SEV	ADF	- 1.853337 (0.3458)	- 3.800049 (0.0112)	-3.800049 (0.0112)	--	Trend and intercept	I(1)
	PP	- 1.926190 (0.3145)	- 4.103192 (0.0146)	-4.103192 (0.0146)	--	Trend and intercept	I(1)
IN&COM	ADF	- 0.568291 (0.8571)	- 3.554333 (0.0177)	-3.554333 (0.0177)	--	Trend and intercept	I(1)
	PP	- 0.745317 (0.8128)	- 3.783014 (0.0177)	-3.783014 (0.0177)	--	Trend and intercept	I(1)
RE-ES	ADF	- 3.756321 (0.0112)	0.206442 (0.9656)	-4.131966 (0.0053)	--	Trend and intercept	I(0)
	PP	3.756321 (0.0112)	- 1.853337 (0.3458)	-4.411159 (0.0030)	--	Trend and intercept	I(0)
GDP	ADF	0.116321 (0.014)	- 1.926190 (0.3145)	-4.628597 (0.0019)	--		
	PP	-0.16321 (0.022)	- 0.568291 (0.8571)	-3.800049 (0.0112)	--		

P-values at 5% statistical significance

Source: Author's Computation using R

The table above shows the unit root of each variable at level and first difference. Two methods of test of stationarity are used, Augmented Dickey-Fuller test and Phillip-Perron test. Both tests give the same result about the stationarity of the variables. However, all the variables Agriculture,

Mining and Quarrying, Service, Information, Real Estate, and GDP at Current Price, are stationary at third difference. Since the series were integrated of order one or I (1) in the terminology of Johansen and Nielsen (2016), and their first differences were stationary and also trend and intercept equation is preferable for the variables.

Coefficients:	MA1	MA2	intercept
	-0.3638	-0.2791	2611.153
S.E.	0.1606	0.1615	1433.174

Sigma² estimated as 535795578: log likelihood = -447.5, AIC = 903

Training set error measures:							
ME	RMSE	MAE	MPE	MAPE	MASE	ACF1	
Training set	88.59872	23147.26	16094.16	-10816.91	10966.85	0.6688007	-0.02279323

The analysis for the autoregressive moving average model show that the data was level at zero integration I(0) and also it is clear that the data those not follow the autoregressive model, only the moving average model at lag(2) is required for the ARIMA model. Moving average model at lag 1 (MA1= -0.3638) with standard error 0.1606 and at lag 2 (MA2 = *0.2791) with a standard error = 0.1615 and AIC = 903 implies that the moving average model is not stable with a high sigma*2 estimate and a high aic coefficient which make is a bad and insignificant model for the prediction of GDP in Nigeria. The error measurement from the analysis shows that the model is 10966.855% inaccurate in the prediction of GDP at Current Price which is an outrageous value that is not interpretable considering the estimate of the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) this is due to the presence of global and local outlier inflated into the data.

4. Conclusions and Recommendation

When using time series models for seasonal adjustment or short-term forecasting, the treatment of outliers is of prime importance. Two methods are explored are i. the automatic outlier identification and modification, ii. Identification of external causes and simultaneous of estimation of outliers.

The study came to conclude that throughout the research, it was established that in the presence of outliers, the forecasts with the adjustment of outliers are better than the forecast without adjusting for outliers. Since the procedures are based on simple techniques, they are widely applicable. For instance, they can be used as data screening device in spectral density estimation and in robust time series analysis. They can also be used in biological study where exogenous disturbances are unavoidable. For example, Box & Tiao (1979) analysed body temperature of an individual involved in a psychiatric study where the observations clearly depended on the individual physical activities. Therefore it is good to note that a variance changes in GDP time to time seems highly plausible. A third application of the procedures is that they can be used to identify the time point of an intervention in the intervention analysis of Chang & Tao (1983). Generally, in the traditional

intervention analysis, the time point of an event is assumed to be known. The study supports the claim that outliers do result in model misspecification as they affect the autocorrelation structure within any time series data. In our case it is illustrated initially that the best model is the ARIMA (0 1 1) that could be fitted to our data. Thereafter, testing the residuals for normality and constant variance showed that both assumptions were violated although the parameters in the model were insignificant for the outlier adjusted model. Using such model for forecasts would have given misleading figures for a decision maker, this is also confirmed in the GDP at current Price figure 4.3 above which is possibly attributed to the presence of outliers.

Based on the findings from this study, the following remarks are made on the procedures for outlier detection. First, the adjusted series was used in the detection process to demonstrate the usefulness of the suggested model (Multiple Regression Analysis and Autoregressive Moving Average Model) procedure. This, however, does not imply that one cannot rely on the data without adjusted outlier series to make inferences, estimating jointly the impact of disturbances and the time series parameters. This strategy allows for the use of prior information of the disturbances. It can also reduce the possibility of over parameterization that arises from the abuse of the detection procedure.

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